

SUBJECTIVE UNIVERSE

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ABSTRACT

Subjectivity, that banished from science, contains the vastest evidence that leads to life. In this work, we will see how to characterize it from the Transcursive Logic. We will also learn that the most conspicuous defenders of reason and objectivity, such as the Greeks, gave it their place, although this is only evident in a "second reading" of their works. The subject-object relationship, an aspect of reality that has unveiled man for more than 2,500 years, is the deep foundation that the Transcursive Logic uses to characterize subjectivity, their Universal Language, and the subjective universe, or that real stratum where the subject acquires the knowledge necessary to stay alive.

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1.0. INTRODUCTION

Subjectivity as a concept has a not so distant history, which goes back, not to the change brought about by the Pre-Socratic from *phýsis* to the *polis*, where a subject who makes a social use of language can be discovered, pondering his discourse and relating it to the episteme, but Descartes who linked it to the substantial, passing through the empiricists who assigned him the representation of the mental based on experience, until he reached Kant, who stripped it of the substance and endowed it with a self that erected a logical unit with the ability to judge experience.

The "linguistic turn" fostered in philosophy by the logical positivists at the dawn of the 20th century, whereby the empire of the reason was replaced by the empire of language, diluted all previous assignments. From then on, it was possible to continue distinguishing the world from the subjective, but regardless of internal facts. A summary is seen in Figure 1.

- S.
- XVII **DESCARTES: EGO = THINKING SUBSTANCE**
- ↓ **EMPIRISTS: EGO = SUBJECT REPRESENTING THE EXPERIENCE**
- ↓ **KANT: EGO = SUBJECT THAT JUDGES THE EXPERIENCE**
- XX **LOGICAL POSITIVISTS: CHANGE REASON FOR LANGUAGE, AND THE EGO FOR THE SPEAKING SUBJECT**

Fig. 1 PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH TO THE CONCEPT OF SUBJECTIVITY
(Salatino, 2017)

The previous figure shows the two opposite poles between which subjectivity was trapped; that is, between the subjective-internal or reason defended by Kant, and the objective-external or language, sponsored by logical positivists. Meanwhile, the subjective-external of the empiricists and the objective-internal of Descartes ended up being the basis of epistemology, that is, the theory of knowledge that generates for

itself, a particular language that allows naming to define. Defining is not knowing, which means that epistemology ends up being the slave of its terms that “define” using a jargon of second knowledge that rests on a prior and *a priori* knowledge (mathematical character of cognition) (Juanes, 2013, p . 54)

The Ego becomes an absolute domain of language and therefore, the old Aristotelian semiotic equation: Reality-Thought-Language, that is, where three different locations of the Ego were posed: one internal, another external and an intermediate third, it is reduced to a single dimension that is projected in three different strata: mind, subject and speech, but with the same social function: the communication, with which the subjective is resigned to the mere 'interpretation' of a discourse, situation in which science in general becomes an accomplice, by relegating the subject to the rear guard of the intellect and its logical thinking, “that self-sufficient thinking that is based on physical-mathematical science, paradigm of clear and simple, universal thinking and impersonal, ordered and in accordance with irrefutable laws” (op. cit., p. 53); consummate in this way, the triumph of logocentrism, which sustained on the rational, logical and objective, that conditions, limits and disqualifies, leading to an inert and mechanical rigidity.

All of the above gives rise to different conceptions of the mind-body relationship, which ultimately end up being a way of characterizing the relationship that links the subject to the object. Figure 2 tries to synthesize these relationships.

Fig. 2 DIFFERENT CONCEPTIONS OF THE SUBJECT-OBJECT RELATIONSHIP
(Salatino, 2017)

We see in the figure that the characterization of an **internal object** that maintains a direct relationship with language gave rise to *Functionalism*¹. An **internal subject** with an indirect relation to language gave rise to *Freudism*.

An **external object** that promotes a direct relationship with language originated *Pragmatism*² and finally, an **external subject** that establishes an indirect relationship with language generated *Lacanism*.

Both *Functionalism* and *Lacanism* have absolutely linguistic support, so they are excluded from this analysis as they, in turn, lack any scientific support.

Pragmatism responds exclusively to cultural norms derived from the different forms of social life or from 'language games'³ that define a social context, leaving everything to a causally determined action which, as in the previous cases, does not withstand the slightest analysis.

Consequently, we only have the *Freudian* proposition as the only possibility to scientifically approach subjectivity, since it considers a subject that inhabits an internal world. Psychoanalysis is a proposal for the study and interpretation of human subjectivity.

Psychoanalysis, like the subjective science it purports to be, does not comply with the principle of falsifiability as Popper (1980) demands, nor can it show the external consistency, or the relationship with other recognized sciences, that Bunge (2002) demands, to not be considered a pseudoscience. Furthermore, it cannot even count on the help of the so-called "Social Sciences" because these, which supposedly are dedicated to the study of man as subject, strictly speaking, are not either.

Freud and the subsequent good attempts lacked the ideal tool that would allow the scientific approach to subjectivity; This is the role that Transcursive Logic intends to fulfill.

¹ Cognitivism doctrine maintains that if the brain states are mental states it is because they have a certain type of function in the general behavior of the organism. The functionalist define mental states in terms of causal relationships, and these, in principle, could be found in anything. In this way, functionalist analysis presumes to be a conceptual truth that analyzes mental concepts in causal terms. One of its initiators was H. Putnam. Who initiated this current of thought in Psychology was J. Fodor, the fundamental foundation of current Psycholinguistics (Author's Note).

² A philosophical current that is based on establishing the meaning of things through consequences; it is based on *ex-post* judgments and avoids all prejudice. What is considered practical or not depends on considering the relationship between utility and practicality (Author's Note).

³ Referring to Wittgenstein's proposal, which conceives language, no longer as a figure of reality, but as an instrument or as a tool. The philosopher's task is to know the words in their daily use, their meaning since it is what language games express. The sense is given by a specific context (Author's Note).

To scientifically address subjectivity it is an unavoidable condition not to confuse it with identity (Hall, 2004, p. 3); otherwise, we will inevitably come to believe that subjectivity can be defined in terms of an epistemological/ontological intersection, which would only serve to socially characterize our existence according to organized collective knowledge (governed by norms), but nothing more.

2.0. ON SUBJECTIVE REALITY

The Transcursive Logic (TL) shows us a reality that is not a wasteland devoid of life, but quite the contrary, it is what contains everything possible thanks to life, but that cannot be shown directly, but only through of its unmistakable manifestations. Subjective reality is everything that is not seen, but it is perceived and felt and to which every living being has to respond in the hard work of inscribing, in 'own flesh', its history. That which affects us directly and is indirectly manifested by its presence. From subjective reality, there is no sense in distinguishing between reality and fiction, because the assembly of all possible worlds is the only possible world outside of the monocontexture.

The vision that our subjective reality gives us, about everyday reality is pure fiction; it is like the sound of the bell used by the blind person to 'see' the time on the church bell tower clock. Subjective reality is transparent, does not cast any shadow, does not leave a mark on the road, although it does on the subject that holds it. The TL allows us to investigate those traces and project them into the behavior and the evident conduct, without feeling the influence of schemes and formalities that respond to a specific law in force in the monocontextural content.

In subjective reality, what makes sense and what does not have it, is not irrevocably determined by a sociocultural convention, but by what "becoming flesh" can be related to the only environment in which it is possible to survive. To project the subjective is not to make the fantastic, the hallucinatory, the transitory alienation of idleness perfectly daily and natural, nor to convert into law a feeling of unreality. It is to show the evolutionary history that allowed every living being, according to its complexity, to go through the cumulative stages of subject, individual, and person, as the case may be. That is the task of the TL.

The subjective reality, seen from the monocontexture (from our universe) presents characteristics that make it opaque to our ignorance, because as we have already said, it is not shown directly, but rather suggested. Its internal timelessness as a dreamlike warp, the lack of a net limit between life and death, the split identity, the

subject/object coexistence are some of the factors that link it to the existence of every living being.

It is as if this strange world, despite being as unique as it is, was the product of a delusional attack that forced the subject to express himself in an incomprehensible and unknown language, at least, for the "sane" that inhabit the monocontexture. It is a manifestation that, being contrary to the rules and norms that force us to a limitless conception of our limited world, empowers us to have a perception, neither better nor worse, but different from reality.

Subjective reality is that ineffable domain where we can get to true knowledge (with sense) and "embodied" knowledge that can be reached without any empirical verification, nor is there any logical or rational support that ensures strict compliance with the so-called "laws of nature," those that seeing from the polycontexture, seem to be mere *obiter dicta*⁴.

Not always, when what is perceived does not coincide with the evidence shown, we are facing insanity. We could say without fear of being too wrong, that when this occurs it is because some unusual contact has occurred between the apparent objective reality and the inescapable subjectivity.

Subjective reality has no relation to the religious, poetic, and metaphysical worldviews that Dilthey (1949) raised in his "Sciences of the spirit", nor to paradigms that are undergoing an update in an attempt to overcome the obsolescence of old schemes. It has to do with truths or beliefs, needs, or desires that make us "see", individually, a universe in which our life, our knowledge, and our natural language settle.

This reality, which involves a vital, psychical, and social activity, is not related to the objectivity that science tries to impose, nor the logic that supports it or the philosophy that justifies it. Therefore, it is not conditioned by the degree of social development, nor by the scientific status, nor the level of education. Ideologies, religions, science, or political doctrines influence everyone's conception of reality-based strictly on the beliefs or social truths that are a direct consequence of the urgent need that we have to be considered us.

Each living being can form an internal structure that allows him to adapt to stay alive. In a way, it could be said that each subject generates a "model" of the environment in

⁴ Simple sayings, that never end up being laws (Author's note).

which he learns to maintain his life, to "dialogue" with his environment, and to relate with their peers. It is not a "static internal image" that, with one-to-one correspondence and tied to a specific time, gives us the basic information of a supposed 'absolute truth', as modern theories try to make us believe, considering space as the "container" of said reality. In this internal structure that we are proposing, lies the possibility of generating a subjective reality that, depending on the complexity of the living being in question, maybe constructed through its biology, or biology plus the activity of its nervous system, or of both, plus their sociocultural activity.

According to the above, the last of the subjects representing man has an adaptive-evolutionary accumulation of elements that allow him to face his reality. This does not mean that, also, the human being has the possibility of making a better evaluation of that, his reality, according to a series of 'attachments' of a social nature and therefore apparent, which place him, supposedly, at the top of the evolutionary chain. Or put another way, even if we get a different answer to the question What is reality ? made to people with different levels of education, it does not mean that they "understand" that reality according to common sense that allows an empirical explanation. Neither, from a critical vision that supports a scientific explanation, far from it, from supposed first causes within a natural order that justify, without doing so, a fundamental and systematic reflection.

Every living being has the reality they need. For that reason, any defining claim is meaningless, except for that of man who, being immersed in a system he tries to define, being part of that definition, is unable to sustain an "objectivity" that reaches the immeasurable limits that are assigned to it. The simple fact of having to comply with a mere convention does not let you see the reality behind the appearance.

Every living being has the reality that his evolutionary level allows him to recognize; therefore, it is dependent on its bio-external system, and within it, on the nervous system or its equivalent. In the case of man, it has nothing to do with the naive conception that Kant had in this sense and that in one way or another, it has been and is the one that supports science, especially modern research.

This does not mean that each species "sees" the universe that surrounds it differently, according to its biological differences, but that, and according to its level of complexity, as we have already said, it constructs said reality according to its needs but guided by a single language; a universal language that associates them with everything that has or serves to generate life.

3.0. THE GUIDELINES OF THE LIVING

According to our approach, something can be considered alive if:

- a. The origin, order, and function of the basic elements that allow life are inseparable and universal.
- b. If instead of showing us a 'snapshot' of his present, he reflects his history and his clear intention to survive.
- c. If he does not exhibit a precise boundary between him and what is lifeless.
- d. If elemental units that are evolutionary intervene in its conformation, which makes the 'living' more than 'units of life'.
- e. If their primordial forms are simpler (or less complex) than the final forms, even if both start from the same basic structure.
- f. If it has at its 'base' the same logical structure of relations "as everything that lives." If it is governed by the same universal language as everything else.
- g. If their living condition arises from the distinction between a superficial (apparent) level and a profound (hidden) level. And, how the profound level is projected onto the surface, giving rise to a change or transformation between the quantitative and the qualitative, generating a cycle that begins indefinitely again.
- h. Whether the emergent (apparent) properties are discrete, while those that control profound transitions are continuous.

Therefore, the major criteria necessary to understand the living, as presented here are order, disorder, change, frontier, cyclical behavior, and its dimensions: structural (1D), dynamics (2D), functional (3D) and transcendent (4D). These guidelines could be further narrowed if we said that the enigma of life is restricted to solving a single problem: finding sense to reality with the sole intention of surviving.

The process of giving sense to the real that we will know here as "semiosis" or "semic act" is not restricted to a Biosemiotics or semiotics of life. Rather, it is considered as a true living process where 'the opposite aspects' merge into a complex unit that, in total agreement with everything real, becomes a sign of mediation between contextures.

This cyclical process is the hidden motor that promotes leaps in time in the living being, due to the fine one-way line of the eternal present that separates its past from its preterite-future⁵.

The "semiosis" is considered as the fruit of an evolution that never ends and that has brought life and its expressions to what we know today. In this evolution, the living was acquiring a "universal language" (UL) which is the one that structures all reality as a whole.

The environment was likely structured first and followed by dabbling in life that to previously differentiate and maintain that difference later, they had to assimilate the logical (relational) structure of their surroundings. Configured "logically" themselves homologously, they learned and were able to evolve, that is, they survived.

Subsequently and as a consequence of having developed an internal control system, the central nervous system (CNS), the possibility of structuring based on the same UL, incarnating them, would have emerged, the management of certain processes that, due to repetition, they were automated and served to a better adaptation to the demands and a greater aptitude to maintain their life condition.

The exponential growth in the complexity of the different systems developed promoted a greater consumption of resources. The early exhaustion of these forced to replace them and the way of replacement split the biological world into two large subsystems. On the one hand, that of vegetables and simple beings that either generate their resources using the environment or have them at hand. On the other hand, that of the animals in which their CNS allows them to search for the livelihood that they were unable to produce, forcing them to travel extensively.

The life-threatening dangers on the long road to achieving livelihoods force the structuring of an alert mechanism to protect against such threats. The proto-psyche

⁵ "What was, will be." There is an answer before the future is present. This future is not a "desirable future", that is, it is not a possible future conditioned in cause and effect, but only in the cause, because of something that happened previously. We could somehow resemble it a "futurable" (What will happen in the future only if certain conditions exist), for being similar to the *desirable future* of Bertrand de Jouvenel (1967, p. 18) and I say similar because here, unlike what is proposed by this French author, desire does not necessarily originate in a questioning of the present situation, whose origin is in what was learned in the past, but because it originated and is satisfied in the past, it determines the future. "*If something were not what it was, surely it is not what it seems to be.*" This is not to do 'foresight' or imagine a future, it is to predict the future to fulfill a single wish: to stay alive. It should not be confused with the previous future verb tense that describes an action that is going to take place in the future, but that has already been completely defined in the past, that is, it indicates an anteriority of the action. In the past tense, nothing is said about the action itself, only about the fertile past, it is also not a verb tense. It is a vital time! (Author's Note).

arises, which also allows better control of the automatic mechanisms arising from experience⁶.

The emergence of other individual organisms made it imperative the emergence of some means of communication between them, to ensure two important aspects: first, to survive, through reinforcing individual tasks with the group to prolong life, and secondly, to perpetuate the species. The above suggests that, outside the UL that supports the structure of all reality, another language appeared that was used as a means of communication between peers, but not to transmit information between them but as a way of achieving different levels of the reorganization of the surrounding reality. All for the sole purpose of greater and more adequate adaptation, this language is natural language (NL).

Figure 3 summarizes the *semiosis* process described above.

Fig. 3 SEMIOSIS AS AN EVOLUTION OF THE UNIVERSAL LANGUAGE
(Salatino, 2009)

4.0. KNOWLEDGE AS A SUBJECTIVE SCAFFOLDING

The knowledge to which the TL alludes as sustenance of subjectivity does not refer to that defended by Plato, whose basis is the reason. Understanding by "reason" the

⁶ "The psychic processes were born [...] under the selective pressure, they have a conservation value of life and the species [...]" (Lorenz & Leyhausen, 1979, p. 6).

means or instrument whose purpose is knowledge in the broad sense, and which is used to found the truth or at least the plausibility of the statements that speak of certain objects (Roetti, 2014, p. 16).

For the LT, knowledge, although it is based on the "truth", this does not refer to a foundation of reason, but the "sense" that our psyche finds in a real fact, that is, the necessary tool to adequately respond to the requirements of the environment, to be able to stay alive. When that "sense" is found, that is, we have been able to adapt to our environment, then we have acquired the "true knowledge", that which will be engraved with "letters of fire", not in our reason, but our "flesh", and it will give rise to the psychic structure that shapes our experience, that is, our history.

The Platonic characterization of reason has a flaw, since it falls into a fallacy of circularity (*regressus in infinitum*) when it is based on true statements that must be substantiated, in addition to one or more rules that allow those statements to constitute the justification of the thesis, rules that will also require a foundation (Ibidem, p. 17). However, from the LT it can be argued that this circularity is not "vicious", but "virtuous".

4.1. KNOWLEDGE ACCORDING TO PLATO

From the Transcursive Logic, the Platonic approach can be considered as a functional PAU (Salatino, 2019). That is, a 'confrontation' between two species: *episteme* and *doxa*, which as we see in the Figure 4 observe a triple relation of opposition, complementarity, and concurrence or simultaneity. These relationships are derived from their codes that are assigned according to the attached table of a pair of attributes. Plato divided the species, in turn, into two genera. Thus, *episteme*: *dianoia* and *noesis*, while *doxa*: *eikasía* and *pistis*. These divisions are opposed in pairs. That is, the discursive reason (*dianoia*) to belief (*pistis*), while the imagination or ignorance (*eikasía*) to intuitive knowledge (*noesis*).

Finally, we mark the elemental dependencies: the beliefs of the subject, the discursive reason of the object, the evident transformation (what links the subject to the object) that involves both, and the imagination that does not include anyone in particular. We must bear in mind that the functional PAU, alternately, records the subject and the object. In other words, when the *doxa* is the patrimony of the subject, the *episteme* is the patrimony of the object and vice versa. (a dialogical game).

Fig. 4 PAU OF KNOWLEDGE
 References: ⊕: XOR - ⊙: Equivalence

The dynamics suggested by the scheme are the following: all part of the “imagination”, from there, and through “reason”, the discursive reason (go from the premises to the conclusion) can be composed to reach the genuine (intuitive) knowledge conforming *episteme*. But it is also possible to come through a belief, through “truth” (a belief by conviction) to *noesis*. Regardless of the route through which one arrives (direct by reason, or indirectly through the truth) everything cycles until it reaches where we started: imagination or absolute ignorance, to restart the cycle again. This is a way to give foundation the evolution of knowledge (by adaptation as in the TL).

5.0. EISEGESIS OF AN ALLEGORY

Plato mentions an ‘organ of the soul’ (Plato, VII 518d) [Which, perfectly, we could assimilate it to our psyche], and to Dialectics, as a research method that allows us to achieve true knowledge of reality, correcting errors.

He describes the ‘excellences of the soul’, which seem to be closer to the body, such as those that, if not previously present, can later be implanted by habit and exercise. This is equivalent to the experience that is ‘represented’ as knowledge in the cerebral cortex, each time we find sense in a real event, forming part of the psychic structure, and as a response, in the operative memory of the cerebellar cortex (Salatino, 2014).

"Appearance - according to Plato (VII 523b) - offers no confidence and therefore does not stimulate intelligence because it does not elicit two contrary perceptions. [Mention of the dialectical method]. It is natural - he says - that in such cases the soul appeals to reasoning and intelligence to try to examine, firstly, if each thing that is transmitted to it is one or two ... if they seem two - it continues - each one will seem one and different from the other; - and later - if each of them is one and both are two, he will think that they are two if they are separate, because if they are not separate, he will not think that they are two, but one. "

"Sight does not 'see' the big and the small [He gives the example of the little and big fingers of the hand] separately but confused [they are both fingers]. To clarify this, the intelligence that is forced to distinguish them from their similarity must intervene. "

The above allows him to talk about the visible [For us, the apparent or objective reality], where objects are 'united' by their differences (pinkie + middle → fingers); and the intelligible (For us the deep or subjective reality), where objects are 'separated' by their similarities (pinkie [smaller finger] or middle [greater finger]).

With this approach we separate ourselves from the Platonic method of *diairesis* or division, which aims to achieve a definition utilizing a classification of species, dividing the genera.

We only rescue the fact of suggesting that through *synagogé* (union) and *diairesis* (division or separation) one can come to consider the unity of the multiple that points to the essence; that is, to the truth. Later we will see the importance of this scheme in TL.

The Platonic dialectic considers that the activity of reason is the only means to achieve being, through a thorough knowledge of the idea of good, the foundation of all reality. Or put another way, the knowledge of objective reality is that which is derived from the knowledge of the intelligible world, the only way to escape the slavery of perception, of the sensible, of the opinionable. The conception that words more, words less, represents the science of today.

We see that Plato, despite his intention to achieve an ascension of being, did the opposite, since he changed a real appearance (objective, if you will) based on perception, for an ideal or theoretical appearance that based on the intelligible it is not enough to characterize our reality (Figure 5).

The TL, on the other hand, suggests that subjective reality is the true reality and not just an interpretation of it. It is not a 'mental construction' that conflicts with the facts

by not adhering to the demands of strict reasoning, nor is it a forged reality arranged under a rational guise. It is the "bridge" stretched over the indisputable gap that exists between sensible things and thought.

*Fig. 5 ALLEGORY OF THE CAVE
(Salatino, 2017)*

6.0. CONCLUSION

Subjective reality is that variation of existence that every living being resorts to so that the materiality that surrounds it can be transformed into "embodied knowledge." The cornerstone of all experience and therefore, in the construction of a history. From there, life pressures the subject with the periodic, almost endless passing of his history that less emphatically denies a real identity with a preconceived plan, than what is based on a belief, at the evolutionary end. Believing in the ultimate truth that gives reality to a subject when a real fact makes sense; that is when it exudes the absolute certainty that allows it to survive despite its onslaught and can change it by structure, with a clear intention to continue building. "In the more elementary instances, the only truth is life."

The structural that arises from an incessant approach of things to knowledge, decants its identity character towards the roots that ends with the fickle diversity of the appearance. The subjective reality, then, makes its dynamic foundation manifest by fulfilling the non-trivial function of legitimizing the identity between the union of apparent diversity and the separation of its coincidences. This dissolution of the classical principle allows that be assembled and made lawful an opposition to where previously there was, only, pure equality.

The antagonism raised is not exclusive as required by objective paraphernalia, but conservative as suggested by Hegel (1816-1985). Opposites, while complimentary, do not share a common dimension, but a relational pattern of their dimensions where the circumstance of participating in any entity is equivalent to 'as if' they were. This legitimate ambiguity is a function of both the subject and the object, which is why it offers greater options than the stable objective eventuality, by regenerate based on error unknown aspects of reality.

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